

Does the growing of Bt maize change abundance or ecological function of non-target animals compared to the growing of non-GM maize? A systematic review

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Additional file 2: References included in the full text screening

References included in the quantitative database and/or the narrative summary tables. References were assigned a unique identifier (publication number). References used for the database are labelled with “DB”. References used for the narrative summary tables are labelled with N1-N5 according to the table number in Additional file 3.

The sources (bibliographic databases, full text databases, specialist search, personal contacts, reviews) for each reference are included. Databases are abbreviated as follows: WOS: Web of Science Core Collection; BIO: BIOSIS; ZOO: Zoological Record; SCI: SciELO; AOA: Agricola; AGS: AGRIS; CAB: CAB Abstracts; BAS: BASE; PRO: ProQuest; GOO: Google Scholar; JST: JSTOR; SCO: Scopus. See Additional file 1, Table S1.1 for details.

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The sources (bibliographic databases, full text databases, specialist search, personal contacts, reviews) for each review are included. Databases are abbreviated as follows: WOS: Web of Science Core Collection; BIO: BIOSIS; ZOO: Zoological Record; SCI: SciELO; AOA: Agricola; AGS: AGRIS; CAB: CAB Abstracts; BAS: BASE; PRO: ProQuest; GOO: Google Scholar; JST: JSTOR; SCO: Scopus. See Additional file 1, Table S1.1 for details.

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- Ex01: No original data (off-topic reviews, summaries, abstracts, opinion papers, etc.)
- Ex02: Same data published in other article with higher quality (e.g., peer-reviewed paper), more detail, or more suitable format
- Ex03: No animal populations naturally inhabiting fields (or their margins) were sampled (e.g., laboratory studies)
- Ex04: Study on target pests (Lepidoptera-targeted maize: *Busseola fusca*, *Chilo partellus*, *Diatraea grandiosella*, *Diatraea saccharalis*, *Helicoverpa zea*, *Helicoverpa armigera*, *Heliothis* spp., *Ostrinia nubilalis*, *Ostrinia furnacalis*, *Striacosta albicosta*, *Sesamia nonagrioides*, *Spodoptera frugiperda*, and *Spodoptera exigua*; Coleoptera-targeted maize: *Diabrotica* spp.)
- Ex05: No Bt maize grown in the field
- Ex06: No appropriate comparison to corresponding non-Bt maize
- Ex07: No data on abundance or activity density, predation or parasitization rate, species richness, biodiversity, or community structure, or other measure for animals in the Bt / non-Bt comparison.
- Ex08: unreplicated experiment (only one Bt and non-Bt field)
- ExDUP: duplicate reference not detected automatically
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